

TRANSCRYSTALLINITY IN THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITES: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE - MECHANICAL PROPERTY RELATIONSHIPS

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical implications of transcrystallinity are presented for two systems which were investigated using separate experimental approaches that were chosen to ascertain the mechanical properties of the transcrystalline interlayer and its role in a composite. The first system is that of an aramid fibre-reinforced nylon 66 microcomposite, where isolated strips of transcrystalline material were obtained by microtoming. The storage modulus and the viscoelastic energy damping component were tested in tension using dynamic mechanical thermal analysis. The second system is a high modulus carbon fibre-polycarbonate, single-fibre composite in which a transcrystalline layer was grown on the fibre prior to bulk matrix crystallisation. In this case a thermal fragmentation process was used to investigate thermal stresses.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composite materials offer significant advantages over well established thermosetting systems in that commodity materials such as polyolefins and nylons can be used and adapted to meet more demanding design specifications without resorting to more expensive polymer systems. Unlike thermosetting matrices which are amorphous, thermoplastic matrices may be partially crystalline and the degree of crystallinity as well as the physical order of the polymeric matrix are expected to play a major role in determining the mechanical performance of the composite. The effect of the matrix morphology, however, is not straight forward and a direct correlation between the matrix crystalline order and the mechanical properties of the composite is not always expected. This results from the fact that the mechanical properties are also expected to depend on the fibre-matrix interaction at the interface.

In thermoplastic matrix composites a transcrystalline layer may develop on the surface of the fibre. An ordered transcrystalline growth depends both on the nucleation capacity of the fibre surface and on the crystallisability of the polymer. It has been shown previously that the growth of a transcrystalline layer obeys thermodynamic considerations and heterogeneous nucleation theory. Although many researchers have attempted to show the effect of a transcrystalline layer on

the mechanical properties of composite materials no universal argument has ever established the role of the interphase satisfactorily. This is in part due to the difficulty in growing a transcrystalline layer on the fibre surface without also changing the morphology of the bulk matrix. Hence, it is also difficult to attribute changes in the composite mechanical performance solely to the presence of a transcrystalline layer.

This research approached transcrystallinity in two ways: Firstly, transcrystalline layers were removed mechanically from Kevlar-49/nylon 66 microcomposite specimens by microtoming. The isolated layers were then tested to determine the mechanical properties by measuring the dynamic mechanical properties and thermal expansion coefficients. The morphology of the transcrystallinity, which was measured using an X-ray diffraction method, identified the direction of the chain folding axis for the nylon 66 system and explained the orientation differences in the thermal expansion coefficients exhibited by the microcomposite specimens. Secondly, the transcrystalline layer was isolated by using a polycarbonate system. This thermoplastic, which is generally considered to be amorphous, crystallises with the appropriate thermal treatment. Due to the different induction times for bulk and surface crystallisation, it was found that a transcrystalline layer could be grown on the surface of the carbon fibre system prior to bulk matrix crystallisation. Thermal fragmentation tests which can be used to determine the compressive thermal stresses in the fibre were used to study the effect of transcrystallinity. Full accounts of the various experimental procedures can be found in a number of papers published recently by our group [1-4] and they will not be repeated here.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two examples are presented to demonstrate the effect of the transcrystalline layer on the mechanical performance of composite materials. The first is the results of a dynamic mechanical thermal analysis of different nylon 66 strip specimens tested in tension. A comparison is presented in Fig. 1 of the storage moduli of 80 μm wide specimens of a quenched, crystallised and transcrystalline (grown on Kevlar-49 fibre) matrix, where the magnitude of the modulus as a function of temperature follows exactly that respective order.

Figure 1. Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis results of the storage modulus for quenched, crystallised and transcrystalline specimens [2]

The results in Fig. 1 (taken from reference [2]) emphasize the prominent effect of transcrystallinity. At 25°C, for instance, the storage modulus of the transcrystalline specimen is 3255 MPa compared with 2480 and 2250 MPa of the crystallized and quenched specimens, respectively. Applying the "rule of mixture" approach to the storage modulus at 25°C, a value of $E'_{tc} = 4633$ MPa for 100% transcrystallinity is obtained, where E'_{tc} is the storage modulus of the transcrystalline layer in the fibre direction. Clearly, the stiffness in the fibre direction of the transcrystalline layer is two fold higher than that of the bulk crystallized matrix.

Now, a similar approach as for the storage modulus can be applied to the coefficient of thermal expansion, by testing strip specimens of the crystallised nylon 66 matrix and of a transcrystalline layer grown on an aramid fibre. The calculation of the thermal expansion coefficient, of a 100% transcrystalline specimen is based on a modified thermal expansion equation as follows:

$$\alpha^L = (E_f V_f \alpha_f + E_m V_m \alpha_m + E_{tc} V_{tc} \alpha_{tc}) / E^L \quad (1)$$

where α , E and V are the coefficient of thermal expansion, the Young's modulus and the volume fraction, respectively, the subscripts f , m and tc denote fibre, matrix and transcrystallinity, and the superscript L denotes the longitudinal properties of the composite. For a transcrystalline strip specimen $V_f = 0$ and at 100°C, for instance, $E_m = 638$, $E_{tc} = 1998$, $E^L = 1128$ MPa and $\alpha_m = 307 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ which results in $\alpha_{tc} = 18 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$. It is seen that the coefficient of thermal expansion of the transcrystalline layer in the fibre direction is more than an order of magnitude smaller than that of the crystallised matrix.

The second example is of thermal compressive fragmentation experiments for high modulus pitch-based carbon fibres in polycarbonate [3,4]. The thermal fragmentation process is based on the fact that as the microcomposite is cooled from the melt through the glass transition temperature of the matrix, a compressive stress is induced in the fibre which eventually results in its continuous fragmentation, where the number of fragments increases with cooling.

Figure 2. Results of thermal fragmentation experiments in carbon fibre-reinforced polycarbonate microcomposites, showing the number of compressive breaks as a function of decreasing temperature for specimens with (□) and without (○) transcrystallinity [4]

As polycarbonate is basically an amorphous thermoplastic, it is considered that the point at which it is sufficiently rigid to support stress is commensurate with its glass transition temperature (150°C), and the stress level is therefore directly proportional to the temperature interval from the glass transition. Despite its basic amorphous nature, polycarbonate can crystallise slowly. Moreover, the induction time for transcrystallisation on the carbon fibre is significantly shorter than for bulk crystallisation. This enabled comparison of the fragmentation phenomenon in the presence of transcrystallinity without changing the amorphous nature of the bulk matrix. Fig. 2 shows an example taken from reference [4]. It is seen that in the presence of a transcrystalline layer a higher thermal stress (a larger temperature interval from the glass transition) was required for the onset of fibre fragmentation. This was attributed to the differences in the thermal strain that was transferred across the matrix to the fibre and is considered to be directly related to the thermal expansion coefficient and Young's modulus of the transcrystalline layer.

CONCLUSIONS

Two kinds of experiments are presented above where, in one, inherent properties of transcrystallinity are measured directly, and in another, mechanical properties of composite materials with and without transcrystallinity are compared. Combining the observations of the two experiments may result in a causative relation between transcrystallinity and performance of composites. The main conclusion of this study is that some of the effects of the transcrystalline layer on the mechanical properties of the composite materials may result from the lower coefficient of thermal expansion and the higher Young's modulus of the transcrystalline layer in the fibre direction compared with the crystallised matrix. These properties of the transcrystalline layer are reflected in the behaviour of the composite materials and in some cases enhance its mechanical performance. An understanding of the relation of the transcrystallinity to the thermal history of the manufacturing of the composite will allow the optimum manufacturing procedures to be defined.

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